

Research Article

Optimized designed electromechanical system based on eddy current for vibration suppression in cantilevered beam

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Abstract: Eddy current is produced when a conducting coil started movement through the static magnetic field or when the magnetic field which is time varying moved through the static conducting coil. Such kind of current when passes through the conducting coil, a magnetic field generates having an opposite polarity that resists to change in magnetic flux. The vibrations in vibrating structures 'using the concept of electromagnetic principle of electromotive force (EMF) combining with a shunt circuit RLC known as electromagnetic shunt damper (EMSD) that dissipate mechanical energy to electrical energy. In this study a newly designed mechanical CAD model along fabricated RLC shunt circuit is used for vibration suppression in cantilever beam. Moreover, some other factors like effect of EMSD distance (1mm, 2mm and 3mm) from coil which is attached with edge of beam and frequency responses on first and second modes are analyzed through experiments and ANSYS simulation. Results revealed that maximum damping ratio 4.92% is achieved at 2mm distance as compare to 1mm (1.93%) and 3mm (1.67%) distance. This work demonstrates that effect of magnetic lines distance from coil play an important role for eddy current generation in electromechanical system for vibration suppression in cantilever beam.

Keywords: Eddy current, electromechanical system, vibration suppression, cantilevered beam

Introduction

Eddy currents are originated by the movement of a conductor through a stationary magnetic field or a period differing Eddy currents are originated by the movement of a conductor

through a stationary magnetic field or a period differing magnetic field through a stationary conductor. These eddy currents progress in the conductive material and are scattered, causing a resistive force between the magnet and the conductor (Cheng & Oh, 2009). These electromagnetic strengths can be utilized to suppress the vibrations of a malleable structure. The vibration suppression of the adaptable structures has been considered as a critical issue in the useful outline of the mechanical, aviation and electrical items. To take care of this issue, such a large number of complex frameworks including new sensors and actuators, different control procedures, and keen materials have been proposed as of recently (Jiang & Gou, 2016). Vibrations are discovered wherever in our environment, some of those are essential, yet as a rule the greater part of the vibrations delivered by regular or man-made means must be suppressed or lessened so to enhance proficiency of a machine, if the vibrations are happening in a machine, or for the general wellbeing of the earth (Cadwell, 2014). People initially wound up noticeably intrigued by vibrations when they first melodic instruments, likely shrieks or drums. Since at that point, the two artists and thinkers have been interested about the laws overseeing the creation of sound from those instruments (Rao, 2010). Many researchers have been established to exploit the eddy currents for damping the vibrations of dynamic systems. For example, eddy current has been used in magnetic braking system, Cantilever beam and vibrating machinery (Ma & Shiau, 2011). The control issue of dynamic reactions for a cantilever beam with a tip mass is regularly experienced in numerous down to earth building applications. Meanwhile, inquires about on unique attributes of actuators utilized as a part of the attractive levitation framework have gotten very consideration in the structure control problems. The attractive levitation methods not just adventure many focal points of no-mechanical-contact suspension, direction and impetus frameworks, yet in addition use the electric current input to evacuate vibration of the levitation body (Wang, n.d.), (“DTIC,” n.d.).

To minimize effect of vibration in ship hull by the dynamic analysis of a beam having a fixed end has been examined through transvers modes of beam, as it was vibrating and an experiment of direct frequency analysis of beam with a point load has been applied. Finally, in the center at different frequencies to check out amplitude with those frequencies at any given point of that beam (Islam & Khalil, 2014). It has been proposed to minimize the vibration in the big and thick beams by increasing the mass or volume of material. This

method was performed with light weight TMD that reduce the vibration in big size beam structures and eddy current (J. S. Bae, Hwang, Kwag, Park, & Inman, 2014),(J.-S. Bae, Kwak, & Inman, 2005). As of late, the piezoelectric shunt damping has turned into a most prevalent strategy for limiting the vibration of the adaptable structures, as the idea of keen materials and structures has been broadly examined to dissipate the mechanical energy (Behrens, Fleming, & Moheimani, 2003). A method to control the vibrations in flexible beam by combing the piezoelectric shunt damper and electromagnetic shunt damper using an equation of PSD and EMSD has been recommended (Yan, Wang, Hu, Wu, & Zhang, 2017). For the enhancement of piezoelectric shunt setup, the modification in design and analyzing the electro-mechanical analogies have been introduced to describe the physical explanation (Park & Inman, 2003).

This study gave a description of the design, modeling and analysis of electromechanical based system which is called electromagnetic shunt damper (EMSD). This practicality, inactively controlled and self-powered electromagnetic shunt damper utilizes a perpetual magnet and a coil with RC circuit. Vibration of cantilevered bar produces actuated current into the loop joined with beam which causes a voltage drop over the RC circuit which is put away and dispersed through the capacitor. Finally, mechanical energy is changed into electrical energy. In this research study CAD model of mechanical system and RLC shunt circuit is introduced. Furthermore, this electromechanical system used to check the effect of EMSD at different position like distance of EMSD from coil which was attached with edge of beam at tip mass. Experiments and ANASYS simulation were done to analyze frequency responses. Highest damping ratio 4.92% is attained when EMSD kept at 2mm distance from beam having coil as tip mass. Such kind of damper can be used in CNC machines to over vibrations during machining process which distorted surfaces mechanical parts due to formation chatters.

Dynamic modeling of cantilevered beam with electromechanical system (EMS)

A. Using Hamilton's principle, the dynamic equations of cantilever beam with the copper coil have been formulated for analytical model. The kinetic (T) and potential strain energy (U) of moving cantilever beam with the effect of copper coil as tip mass can be written as:

Kinetic Energy;

$$T = 1/2 \int_0^L \{M(\frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial t^2}) + m'(\frac{\partial y}{\partial t} \partial(A - g))\} dx \quad (1)$$

Potential Strain Energy;

$$U = 1/2 \int_0^L EI(\frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial x^2})^2 dx \quad (2)$$

Virtual work;

$$\delta W = \int_0^L \{f(x, t) - C \frac{\partial y}{\partial x}\} \delta y dx \quad (3)$$

Where M , m' , g , E , I , f and C are mass of cantilever beam, mass of coil, position of coil, Young's modulus, moment of inertia, external force and inherent damping force of cantilever structure.

The following equations were formulated by putting the value of kinetic energy, potential energy and virtual works in the general equation of motion;

$$\delta H = \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \delta(T - U + W) dt = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$M + m' \delta(A - g) \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial t^2} + C \frac{\partial y}{\partial t} + EI \frac{\partial^4 y}{\partial x^4} = f(x, t) \quad (5)$$

The vibratory motion for a cantilever beam is simply approximated with a shape function, $\varphi'(x)$

$$y(x, t) = \sum_{i=1}^n \varphi'(x) z(t) = \varphi' Z \quad (6)$$

$$\varphi'(x) = \cos h(\beta x) - \cos \beta x - D\{\sin h(\beta x) - \sin(\beta x)\} \quad (7)$$

Here the β is frequency coefficient and D is mode shape coefficient.

$$\therefore D = \frac{\sin(\beta x) - \sin h(\beta x)}{\cos(\beta x) + \cos h(\beta x)}, \quad \therefore x = L$$

With the implement of assumed result of (6) to the equation (5) and doing the integration of (5), then multiplying with shape function an ordinary differential equation is obtained.

$$M\ddot{x}(t) + C\dot{x}(t) + Kx(t) = F(t) \quad (8)$$

$$M = \int_0^L \varphi'(x)[M + m'\delta(A - g)\varphi'(x)dx]$$

$$C = \int_0^L \left\{ \frac{d\varphi(x)}{dx} C \frac{d\varphi(x)}{dx} \right\} dx$$

$$K = \int_0^L \left\{ \frac{d^2\varphi(x)}{dx^2} EI \frac{d^2\varphi(x)}{dx^2} \right\} dx$$

$$F(t) = \varphi \times f^{ext}(x, t) dx$$

Here M,

$$F(t) = \int_0^L f^{ext}(x, t)\varphi dx = [-K_d i(t)\delta(A - g) + f^{ext}(t)\delta(A - b)]\varphi dx$$

$$-[K_d\varphi(g)]i(t) + \varphi(g)f^{ext}(t) = -K_d i(t) + F_{ext}f^{ext}(t)$$

$$K_d = NBL = \text{Electromechanical coupling coefficient}$$

B. With the consideration of external force and electromechanical coupling coefficient in the presence of RLC circuit which acted as electromechanical shunt damper (EMSD), the ordinary differential equations for cantilever beam and RLC circuit can be written as:

$$M\ddot{x}(t) + C\dot{x}(t) + Kx(t) + K_d i(t) = f^{ext}(t) \quad (9)$$

$$L\ddot{i}(t) + Ri(t) + \frac{1}{C_s}i(t) - K_d\dot{x}(t) = 0 \quad (10)$$

Where M, C, K, x are the mass, damping coefficient, stiffness and displacement of cantilever beam. The "f" is external force. While L, R, $1/C_s$ and i are inductance, resistance, capacitance and current flow in the RLC circuit. The K_d is electromechanical coupling coefficient which depend on NBL. If f^{ext} is equal to zero then vibration will considered free vibration.

The magnitude of the frequency response function of cantilever beam with the closed coil acting as electromagnetic shunt damper can be obtained by solving the equation (9) and (10). With the assumption of harmonic response and doing the Laplace transformation the coupled equation for cantilever beam with coil acting as EMSD can be written as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} M & 0 \\ 0 & L \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \ddot{x} \\ \ddot{i} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} C & K_d \\ -K_d & R \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x} \\ \dot{i} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} K_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/C_s \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ i \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Laplace transformation of equation (11)

$$\begin{bmatrix} MS^2 & 0 \\ 0 & LS^2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X \\ I \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} Cs & K_dS \\ -K_dS & Rs \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X \\ I \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} K_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/C_s \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} X \\ I \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} F \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Taking $\begin{bmatrix} X \\ I \end{bmatrix}$ common:

$$\begin{bmatrix} X \\ I \end{bmatrix} \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} MS^2 & 0 \\ 0 & LS^2 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} Cs & K_dS \\ -K_dS & Rs \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} K_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/C_s \end{bmatrix} \right\} = \begin{bmatrix} F \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} X \\ I \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} F \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} / \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} MS^2 & 0 \\ 0 & LS^2 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} Cs & K_dS \\ -K_dS & Rs \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} K_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/C_s \end{bmatrix} \right\}$$

Response Equation

$$H(S) = \frac{X(S)}{F(S)}$$

$$\frac{\begin{bmatrix} X \\ I \end{bmatrix}}{\begin{bmatrix} F \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}} = \frac{1}{\begin{bmatrix} MS^2 & 0 \\ 0 & LS^2 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} Cs & K_dS \\ -K_dS & Rs \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} K_1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/C_s \end{bmatrix}}$$

(11)

Response equation can also be written as:

$$\frac{X^\circ}{F^\circ} = \frac{\begin{bmatrix} X \\ I \end{bmatrix}}{\begin{bmatrix} F \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}}$$

Experimental Setup

In the electronics system a copper coil (having internal resistance $R \approx 79.5 \Omega$, outer diameter

Figure 1: Processing route for films casting

46mm, inner diameter 10mm, thickness 4mm, number of turns 2000, weight 60 grams and three capacitors having capacitance 100 μF shown in figure 1 and double sided adhesive tape having thickness 1mm were used.

Figure 2: CAD model and fabricated mechanical system

A mechanical system was designed and manufactured having a base, slider and slider housing, slider with slider scale and cantilever beam. It was mainly manufactured with Aluminum material due to easy machining and quality. CAD model along machined model is shown in figure 2. During the measurement the experimental setup include an Impact hammer for input having sensitivity 2.25 mV/g, an accelerometer to record the vibrating response of beam having sensitivity 10.45 mV/g, data acquisition card to convert the analog data into a digital form, CutPro software to convert the analog data into graphical form in four different plots for analysis of vibrations shown below in figure 3 (a-d).

Figure 3: (a) Impact Hammer (PCB-086C03), (b) National Instruments DAC, (c) Accelerometer (KISTLER-8778A500), (d) CutPro Software

Results and Discussion

For designing a RLC circuit, there are two rules to be followed which gives different result. Firstly, if a circuit which reaches its final value fast but has minor oscillations along the way is desired then, the circuit should be designed as an underdamped RLC circuit due to its fast response. Secondly, if a circuit is desired which doesn't exceed a certain final value but has no further oscillations, it should be designed as an over-damped circuit.

$$\omega = \frac{1}{\sqrt{LC}}$$

For RLC circuit in series the natural responses are:

- Under-damping:

$$i(t) = e^{st}\{B_1 \cos \omega t + B_2 \sin \omega t\}$$

- Critical damping:

$$i(t) = \{D_1 t e^{st} + D_2 t e^{st}\}$$

- Over-damping:

$$i(t) = \{A_1 t e^{s_1 t} + A_2 t e^{s_2 t}\}$$

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Figure 4: Natural response of a damped RLC Circuit

Figure 5: ANSYS Analysis (Graphical Form & Tabular)

For this experiment, an overdamped circuit was chosen, because this would be employed in an Electromagnetic Shunt Damper, which in turn was being used to suppress vibrations in machining of flexible structure, so further oscillations could cause chatter on the work piece hence negating the effect of the damper. A MatLab plot was made using the data from the ANSYS simulation of the vibration of cantilevered beam. To check the theoretical result of damping of EMSD equation of damping ratio was used that is given below. Which shows the maximum theoretical damping ratio could be provided by the EMSD in an ideal case.

$$\zeta = R/2\sqrt{C/L}$$

Damping factor, $\zeta = \frac{R_T}{2}\sqrt{\frac{C}{L}}$ and $\zeta = 1$. Finally, ω_n obtained 39.0043 Hz that is equal to the results of ANSYS and experimental work shown in figure 4 and 5. On the basis of required parameters of design, the ANSYS results are given below in figures 6 & 7. These figures are shown steps by step method of designing of cantilever beam showing the meshing of solid element having model size 2.5mm which is optimal value for this case. The default number modes for this model are selected 6 while 5 are lateral and 1 torsional.

Figure 6: Meshing

As this is cantilever beam, the load or support conditions are that one end will be fixed and other will be free.

Figure 7: Result of environmental settings

Figure 8: Mode shapes of simply supported cantilevered beam

The theoretical solution is given of all the modes but to get the graphical result of all modes, it is needed to select all the modes and re-solve the model for all the modes to get the mode shape results as shown in figure 15. During this simulation process the modes shapes which are generated without considering the mass of coil are given below in figure 8. Furthermore, As the effect of mass of coil is considered the mode shapes generate different as compare to the mode shapes without coil existence, Further the Frequency at each mode for Beam with coil shown in figure 9 & 14. When the results are compared with and without considering the effect of mass of coil there is a clear difference of frequencies that is shown graphically in figure10.

Figure 9: Mode shapes for beam with coil

Figure 10: Comparison of Beam with coil and without

Similar to the effect of the mass of coil, the effect of base of experimental setup could not be ignored. As the base gave rigidity to hold the setup, it also effects on the vibration of beam. The additional ‘mass result of base’ at ANSYS is shown below in figure11. After the attachment of EMSD, when it started working due to mechanical vibration in beam that might be cause of eddy current. The results comparison was taken at first and second mode shown figure 11 and 13.

Figure 11: ANSYS analysis of beam with mechanical setup

Figure 12: Frequency responses of damped beam on first mode

Figure 13: Frequency responses of damped beam on first mode

Which shown that system was damped more with the effect of eddy current as compare to effect of mass of coil or simply supported beam. To check various factors affecting the damper tuned specifically for aluminum beam of dimensions of 30*330*6 mm. The coil was placed at distance of 2 mm away from the magnets The tuned specifications are $R = 79.5 \Omega$, $L = 55.5 \text{ mH}$, $C = 3 \cdot 100 \mu\text{F}$, and the weight of the coil attached is approximately

60g as mentioned above in experimental section. These tuned settings were for over-damped damper. The capacitors were attached on opposite side of beam hence to avoid attraction between them and the magnets. The results below shown that the damper was able to provide a 56.05% increase in the damping ratio, of which the further test shown that only 16.02% was attributed to the weight of the coil itself. To perform this experiment with controlled situation the various terms were included:

- (a) Simply supported Cantilevered Beam
- (b) With Eddy Current Damper at 2mm
- (c) With coil attached to the beam which acts as Tuned Mass Damper to some extent due to its weight
- (d) With Electromagnetic Shunt Damper at 1 mm
- (e) With Electromagnetic Shunt Damper at 2 mm
- (f) With Electromagnetic Shunt Damper at 3 mm

The chart for their damping ratios is shown below along with their fitted curve shown in figure 16. To reduce the impact of the Eddy Current Damper, it was observed that its impact on the increase in damping proportion was practically immaterial, this was because of the way that eddy current didn't work at that much separation. In any case, as it has been outlined that this damper to work at 2 mm, the estimation of damping proportion at 1 mm and 3 mm is not as high as at it being 2 mm. Additionally, simply like eddy current damper impact turned out to be less that is why its separation among coil and magnet was optimized for better vibration suppression in overall experiment.

Figure 14: Result of environmental settings

Figure 15: Frequency at each mode for Beam with coil

$$\frac{X^\circ}{F^\circ} = \frac{Ls^2 + Rs + \frac{1}{C_s}}{[MLs^4 + (MR + CL)s^3 + (\frac{M}{C_s} + CR + K_1L + K_d^2)s^2 + (\frac{C}{C_s} + RK_1/L)s + \frac{K_1}{C_s}]}$$
 (12)

Figure 16: Comparison of damping ratio on different conditions

Conclusion

The EMSD is well-known to minimize the effect of vibrations in flexible structures. The effect of mass was also discussed that have considerably effect on the damping ratio. The damper was tested to check its effect while changing the physical parameters of damper's environment like magnet distance from the coil and frequencies response on first and second mode. At last, the damper prevailed in significantly damping ($\zeta = 4.92\%$) in an adaptable cantilever beam when put a separation of 3.5 mm from the end and the coil is set 2 mm from the magnet.

Later on, this damper could be improved by testing the impact of non-polar capacitors, and by picking a significantly lighter inductor to take out the impact of mass. This strategy could likewise be connected to machining of adaptable part machining with low frequency vibrations, and if appropriate contraption could be outlined it could be utilized as a shock absorber with higher accuracy in vehicle suspension framework.

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Dedication

Dedicated to my beloved Mother Fouzia Mureed

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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